

TRADITIONAL LESSONS AND ONLINE PROTEIN TRAINING

Saidakhmedova Nurkhon Yusupovna

Associate Professor of the Department
of Chemistry of Kokand State Pedagogical Institute
nurxonsaidaxmedova76@gmail.com +998905507622

Abstract: The methodology of teaching, that is, effective methods and systems of teaching, is developed separately for different age groups and subjects.

Also, within the framework of the reading methodology, attention is paid to the development of students' skills not only in reading text, but also in writing, listening, and speech formation. This generally creates the opportunity to fully master the language and clearly express their thoughts.

Keywords: blended learning, interactive lessons and labs, microlearning, gamification, self-assessment and review, virtual reality.

We can use various teaching methods in teaching the subject of proteins. For example; blended learning, interactive lessons and laboratory work, microlearning, gamification, self-assessment and peer review, virtual reality (VR) and augmented reality (AR), flipped classroom, human-centered pedagogy, etc.

Blended learning, that is, mixed learning, combines traditional classes and online learning. Using this method in teaching proteins allows students to consolidate the topic and review it in a timely manner. For example, after the teacher has presented the information theoretically in the classroom, he can recommend that students consolidate their knowledge through exercises or video lessons on online platforms [1].

Learning proteins should not be limited to theoretical information only. Lessons should be interactive and taught through laboratory work. Interactive lessons attract students' attention and increase their interest in the subject. For example, the teacher can divide students into groups and organize practical exercises with them that demonstrate the process of protein synthesis.

Micro-teaching - provides students with a concise and effective assimilation of information through the presentation of short but meaningful lessons or information. Using this method on the topic of proteins, students are given quick and clear concepts using reinforcement materials or short video lessons. For example, creating a 5-10 minute video lesson on the amino acids that make up proteins allows students to quickly master the basic concepts.

The gamification method increases student motivation by introducing game elements into the learning process. When teaching the topic of proteins, for example, students can be tested through games with several questions. Through games, students feel more engaged and motivated. At the same time, they learn the subject better and participate actively in the lesson.

Self-assessment or peer assessment methods in teaching allow students to consolidate their knowledge and exchange ideas with others. In the topic of proteins, students can learn more by testing their knowledge or by evaluating tasks performed by others in groups.

Virtual reality (VR) and augmented reality (AR) technologies are currently widely used to make the teaching process more effective and interactive. Visualizing the process of learning proteins using these technologies improves students' understanding. For example, students can see the process of protein synthesis using VR, or study the structure of proteins in three dimensions using AR.

The block teaching method consists of teaching the topic to students at home and conducting question-and-answer or practical exercises in the classroom. In this method, the teacher provides students with videos or articles to read, so that students actively participate in practical exercises during the lesson. In the process of teaching proteins, this method gives students the opportunity to master the topic in advance and apply their knowledge in practice in the classroom.

In modern teaching methods, it is important to put students at the center, that is, to use a pedagogical approach based on the needs, interests and learning methods of the student. On the topic of proteins, students can be taught by discussing their knowledge and questions, as well as by analyzing the topic together with them.

Teaching the topic of proteins through modern teaching methods increases student activity, improves the quality of education, and makes the teaching process more interesting. Teachers should use technology and innovative methods in their lessons to prepare students not only to acquire knowledge, but also to apply it in practice.

List of References.

1. Штремплер Г.И., Пичугина Г.А. «Дидактические игры при обучении химии» М.: Дрофа, 2003.
2. M.N. Valixonov. Biokimyo. Toshkent "Universitet". 2009 yil.